

***In silico* modeling, design, synthesis and screening for antitubercular activity of some novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives**

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Abstract : The lead molecule – 1,2,4-triazolin-3-thiones was found to be a powerful novel anti-TB drug with high potency. Isoniazid, the first line drug for TB, will act on the enzyme InhA. An attempt was made to incorporate substituted 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol nucleus to this, so that it will act by inhibiting sterol 14 α -demethylase P450 (CYP51). The lead molecule will be synthesized by conventional method. The products obtained will be characterized and percentage yield calculated. The purity of the compounds will be checked by melting point and R_f value in TLC. Structures of all synthesized compounds were confirmed by FTIR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. Molinspiration software was used for finding the $c \log P$ values and the antitubercular activity was studied. All the synthesized 1,2,4-triazole derivatives showed inhibitory activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv strains.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazoline-3-thione, antitubercular activity, MDR TB, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Introduction

To control the rapid spread of TB, there is an urgent need for new anti-TB drugs with unique modes of action and improved properties like enhanced activity against MDR strains, reduced toxicity, and shortened duration of therapy¹⁻³. The recent rise in incidence of TB and especially the alarming increase of drug resistant TB, call for urgent need to develop new anti-TB drugs. Structure based drug design, targeting multiple enzyme targets on *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is essential for the effective control of TB worldwide. Lead molecule – 1,2,4-triazolin-3-thiones : as a powerful novel anti-TB drug with high potency. Isoniazid, the first line drug for TB, will act on the enzyme InhA. An attempt was made to incorporate substituted 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol nucleus to this, so that it will act by inhibiting sterol 14 α -demethylase P450 (CYP51). In the past decades, triazoles have proved their potential in development of pharmaceutically important organic compounds both of natural and synthetic origin. Triazole analogues have found to have wide variety of pharmacological activities. The high potential of triazole nucleus prompted us to synthesise the title compounds and screen them for their antitubercular activities.

Tuberculosis (TB) caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* continues to be major cause of morbidity and mortality all over the world. WHO has already declared TB as a global crisis. No new anti-TB drug has been brought into the clinic in the past 40 years. Tuberculosis (TB) caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* continues to be major cause of morbidity and mortality all over the world. MDR-TB has been a particular concern among HIV-infected persons. MDR-TB is more difficult to treat than drug-susceptible strains of TB. In this context, there is a need for new drugs to fight against this disease.

Experimental

Materials and methods : All the chemicals were purchased from Aldrich and CDH. Column chromatography was carried out over silica gel (60–120 mesh), purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Melting point were determined in DBK melting point apparatus. IR spectra in KBr disk were recorded from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} on FTIR (Model FT/IR 4100-type A Jasco). ¹H NMR were recorded on ¹H NMR spectrophotometer (Bruker DPX 300 FTNMR) in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are recorded in δ relative to TMS,

the coupling constants are given in Hz. Mass spectra were recorded on an Agilent 1100 MSD mass spectrometer. Molinspiration software was used for studying physico-chemical properties of the title compounds.

Different proposed novel analogues are screened for different physicochemical properties using different software. A few of them will be selected and compared with standard antitubercular drugs and are screened to verify whether they obey Lipinski rule of five and are having drug likeness properties. Analogues with desired physicochemical properties, that is which obeys Lipinski rule of five – drug likeness – are chosen for wet lab synthesis.

General procedure of synthesis of compounds⁴⁻⁷ :

Step 1 : Compounds **3a-h** were synthesized using established methods in the literature. Compound **3a-h** (0.005 mole) was dissolved in 30 mL of absolute ethanol and treated with an ethanolic sodium ethoxide solution [obtained by dissolving sodium (0.005 mole) in 50 mL of absolute ethanol]. After refluxing for 2 h, the reaction mixture was cooled to 30–35 °C and 0.55 mL of ethyl bromoacetate were added. After the addition the mixture was refluxed for 8 h and evaporated at 30–35 °C under reduced pressure. The crude products **4a-h** were purified by recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol. Yield 78%.

Step 2 : To a suspension of compound **4a-h** (0.05 mole) in ethanol (150 mL) 0.06 mole of 99% hydrazine hydrate was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 1.5 h. After cooling the resulting solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-[(4-{[(1)-Phenylmethylene]imino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5a**) : Yield 68%, m.p. 180–183 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3472, 3256 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 3010 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2825 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1610 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.33 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.59–3.8 (2H, S- CH_2), 8.7 and 5.9 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH). MS spectrum, m/z : 354 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)methylene]amino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5b**) : Yield 64%, m.p. 184–185 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3337, 3489 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 3012 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2810 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1612 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.4–7.3 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.8–3.8 (2H,

S- CH_2), 6.7 and 5.5 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH). MS spectrum, m/z : $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)methylene]amino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5c**) : Yield 69%, m.p. 192–193 °C, pale yellow crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3470, 3256 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 3015 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2812 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1678 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1005 ($\text{C}-\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.6 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.5–3.5 (2H, S- CH_2), 7.7 and 5.4 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH), 4.25–3.9 (6H, $-\text{OCH}_3$). MS spectrum, m/z : 414 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(2,4,6-Trimethoxyphenyl)methylene]imino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5d**) : Yield 56%, m.p. 180–183 °C, cream crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3332, 3485 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 3011 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2825 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1610 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1025 ($\text{C}-\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.6 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.7–3.8 (2H, S- CH_2), 4.7 and 5.9 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH), 1.29–1.25 (9H, $-\text{OCH}_3$). MS spectrum, m/z : 444 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(4-Fluorophenyl)methylene]imino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5e**) : Yield 74%, m.p. 174–176 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3232, 3468 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 2960 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2825 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1625 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.33 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.59–3.9 (2H, s- CH_2), 4.8 and 6.5 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH). MS spectrum, m/z : 372 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(4-Methoxyphenyl)methylene]imino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5f**) : Yield 70%, m.p. 194–195 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3472, 3256 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 3004 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2814 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1656 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.2 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.59–3.8 (2H, S- CH_2), 5.7 and 5.9 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH), 1.29–1.25 (3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$). MS spectrum, m/z : 384 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{[(1)-(2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)methylene]imino}-5-pyridin-4-yl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5g**) : Yield 70%, m.p. 178–180 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm^{-1}) : 3462, 3245 ($-\text{NH}_2$), 2967 ($-\text{CH}$ aromatic), 2865 ($-\text{CH}$ of triazole), 1610 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 7.5–7.3 (4H, m, Ar-H), 3.2–3.8 (2H, S- CH_2), 4.7 and 5.9 (2H and 1H, NH_2 and NH). MS spectrum, m/z : 386 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-[(4-{{(1-(*N,N*-Dimethylphenyl)methylene}imino)-5-pyridin-4-yl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio]acetohydrazide (**5h**) : Yield 68%, m.p. 174–176 °C, pale white crystals. IR spectrum (cm⁻¹) : 3453, 3248 (-NH₂), 2950 (-CH aromatic), 2885 (-CH of triazole), 1630 (C=O); ¹H NMR spectrum δ (ppm) : 6.7–7.2 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.59–3.8 (2H, S-CH₂), 5.6 and 5.9 (2H and 1H, NH₂ and NH), 1.5–1.7 (6H, -CH₃). MS spectrum, *m/z* : 397 [M+1]⁺.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the finished compounds from aromatic aldehydes, ethyl bromo acetate and hydrazine hydrate involves five steps. The procedure we adopted was depicted in Scheme 1. Various thioacetohydrazides were the end products. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by IR, NMR, Mass studies. The IR spectra of

Scheme 1

these compounds (**5a-h**) have absorption band in the region of 1610–1678 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the stretching vibrations of the carbonyl group of the amide fragment. There are two absorption bands in the region 3470–3400 cm⁻¹ and 3270–3210 cm⁻¹ that might be interpreted as asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the amino group. These two absorption bands confirm the -CONHNH₂ group in the final compounds. Peaks due to CH stretching vibrations of the aromatic ring were recorded in the interval 3120–2850 cm⁻¹. An intense absorption band is observed in the spectra at 1960 cm⁻¹ due to C-C vibrations of aromatic ring. The chemical shift values of the ¹H NMR spectra also support the structure.

Pharmacological studies :

Antitubercular activity⁸ :

The antimycobacterial activity of compounds **5a-h** was assessed against *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv using microplate Alamar Blue Assay (MABA). The activity is expressed as the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in µg/mL. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration required to complete inhibition of bacterial growth. The MICs of the compounds were depicted in Table 1. All the tested compounds showed better *in vitro* antitubercular activity at minimum concentrations.

Acute toxicity studies :

A prototype molecule, **5c** was randomly selected for the study of safety dose range of the analogues. The compound up to a 1920 mg/kg dose is safe. There is no mortality or gross behavioural change in animals but long term toxicity study is essential for antimycobacterial drugs.

Table 1. Antitubercular activity of triazolothioacetohydrazides

Sl. no	Compd.	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.125	1.6	0.8	0.2	0.1
1.	5a	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
2.	5b	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
3.	5c	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
4.	5d	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
5.	5e	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
6.	5f	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
7.	5g	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
8.	5h	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
9.	Streptomycin	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
10.	Isoniazid	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R

S = Sensitive, R = Resistant.

Conclusion

This research work was focused on the rational approach in design and development of 1,2,4-triazoles as novel antimycobacterial drugs. Research work involved the *in silico* screening of various compounds; synthesis of selected analogues of 1,2,4-triazoles and preliminary pharmacological screening of the analogues. Acute toxicity studies showed that the analogues were safe with low toxicity. Among these analogues eight compounds which obeyed the Lipinski's rule of five, were taken for wet lab synthesis. Purity of the compounds were ascertained by consistency in melting point and R_f value in TLC. The novel analogues were characterized by FTIR NMR and Mass studies. The eight novel synthesized 1,2,4-triazoles were screened for antimycobacterial activity. All compounds showed inhibitory activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv strain.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Govt. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Medical College, Thiruvananthapuram for carrying out the research work and Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Biotechnology for carrying out antimycobacterial studies.

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